

Public debts and State-Owned Enterprises investments: the case of Morocco

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Résumé : Au Maroc, le débat sur la problématique de la hausse de l'endettement public n'a cessé d'augmenter ses dernières années. A ce titre, les pouvoirs publics affirment que celui-ci est la seule issue pour surmonter les contraintes économiques. C'est aussi un moyen nécessaire pour poursuivre l'effort d'investissement public et l'amélioration des indicateurs de l'économie nationale. Notre article a pour objectif de fournir une étude empirique de la relation causale entre l'endettement public, notamment l'endettement des EEP et l'endettement extérieur public avec l'investissement des EEP. L'étude s'est basée sur des données de séries chronologiques annuelles de six variables macroéconomiques pour une période de 27 allant de 1990 à 2016. Les résultats ont permis d'affirmer qu'il y a une relation positive entre l'endettement des EEP et leur investissement à court et long terme.

Mots-clés : Endettement des EEP, investissements des EEP, variables macroéconomiques, modèle à correction d'erreur.

Abstract : In Morocco, the debate on the issue of rising public debt has steadily increased in recent years. As such, the public authorities say that it is the only way to overcome economic constraints. It is also a necessary means to continue the public investment effort and the improvement of the indicators of the national economy. The aim of this paper is to provide an empirical study of the cause relationship between public debt, especially, SOEs debt, external public debt with SOE investment. The study was based on annual time series data for six macroeconomic variables for a period of 27 years from 1990 to 2016. The results indicated that there is a positive relationship between SOEs indebtedness and their investment in the short and long-run.

Keywords : SOEs debt, SOEs investments, macroeconomic variables, error correction mechanism.

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INTRODUCTION

State Owned Enterprises (SOEs) have played and will continue to play an important role in supporting Morocco's strategic reforms, the implementation of public policies and the development of structuring projects, thereby contributing to the improvement of living conditions of the Moroccan citizen.

Given the objectives of accelerated growth on the one hand, and the insufficiency of the internal resources necessary for the financing of investments on the other hand, the use of indebtedness is essential to make up for the insufficiency of the capital required for financing, economic and social development.

Indeed, the SOEs investments went from 16 billion Dirhams in 1990 to 72,7 billion Dirhams in 2016, accumulating a total volume of 1.050 billion Dirhams. And at the same time, the stock of SOEs debt continues to swell in recent years. At the end of 2016, outstanding SOEs debts reached 262,2 billion Dirhams, compared with 242,6 billion Dirhams in 2015, which represents an increase of 7,7% and 51,4 billion Dirhams in 1990.

In this context, the debate on the impact of the public debt on investment has, in recent years, been of considerable importance both in terms of the importance of its economic policy implications and the number of theoretical analyzes and empirical to which it gave rise. However, the relationship between public debt and investment remains theoretically indeterminate. In such a context, the interest of this subject is well established. This is why we propose in this study to analyze the impact of public debt especially SOEs debts and external debts on SOEs' investment.

This study is justified because it is theoretically established that investment contributes to economic growth and development in both developed and developing countries. As such, the main objective of this paper is to examine the effects of the public debt on SOEs investments in Morocco. The analysis will consist of describing the evolution of indebtedness and the investment of SOEs and of identifying their possible links.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this part we will review the literature on the debt and investment relationship, then we will focus on the analysis of the evolution of debts and investments of SOEs in Morocco for the period 1990-2016.

1.1 The debt and investment relationship

Three theoretical approaches have focused on the relationship between indebtedness and investment:

According to the first approach, debt is considered an instrument of economic policy and a preferred means of financing growth. This theory draws its foundations from the Keynesian model (Meade, 1937) according to which indebtedness does not entail any cost neither to present generations nor for future generations because of the new investments that it generates. In this approach, indebtedness favoring the revival of demand driven by the more than proportional accelerating effect of the investment which in turn causes an increase in production. Similarly, external borrowing used to finance productive investment tends to accelerate growth if it is contained within reasonable limits.

On the other hand, for Krugman (1988) and Tabellini & Alesina (1989), who are the proponents of the second meaning, if the future debt of a country tends to be higher than its repayment capacity, the service of its debt will be a growing function of its production, thus discouraging domestic and foreign investors. Fearing that production will be taxed by the State as debt servicing progresses, potential investors will be reluctant to bear immediate costs to increase future production. This is the thesis advanced by the authors of the theory of "over-indebtedness" or the "virtual burden of debt". Over-indebtedness is defined by Claessens & Diwan (1990) as a situation in which external debt is so high that it leads to low investment, even undermining the reduction of debt service.

However, economic theory had come to recognize the existence of a threshold beyond which debt becomes unsustainable. Thus, Barro (1990) has shown that a budget deficit policy financed by borrowing has no effect on economic activity insofar as agents are not victims of fiscal illusion. These agents then anticipate an increase in taxes intended to repay the loan by constituting savings equivalent to public debt. In turn, Hayek (1977) denounced indebtedness as an artificial growth, based on an investment higher than the nation's saving effort and this causing an adjustment by inflation.

Proponents of the over-indebtedness theory suggest that the weakness of investment is due to the existence of a heavy debt burden that reduces the debtor country's incentive to invest. For Krugman (1988), high external debt has a negative potential impact on private investment. Similarly, Faruquee (1992) argues that debt service payments result in the reduction of domestic investment resources. Low international solvency also reduces access to external

savings. In addition, over-indebtedness is a major source of uncertainty. The amount of future transfers, macroeconomic and exchange rate policies are also uncertain.

Over-indebtedness theories have also assumed that inflation reduces private investment by increasing risk, reducing the average maturity of the loan, distorting the informational content of relative prices, and accentuating macroeconomic instability (Dornbusch & Reynoso, 1989; Oshikoya, 1994).

On the other hand, proponents of the third approach attempted to reconcile the two approaches mentioned above by developing models with non-linear effects of debt on investment and growth (Cohen, 1993, 1995). The debt Laffer Curve concept was used in reference to borrowers' prospects of repaying loans before reaching a critical limit to debt accumulation (Husain, 1997). The model assumes that disincentives to invest are associated with a stock of debt placing a country on the wrong side of the curve. Debt Laffer Curve thesis shows that the higher the debt stock, the lower the likelihood of repayment (Pattillo, Poirson, & Ricci, 2011).

Although the models do not explicitly analyze the impact of over-indebtedness on growth, we can deduce that the accumulation of heavy debts slows expansion by slowing down investment in particular. The theory predicts that if the debt is below the critical threshold, there is a tendency to stimulate investment and growth. Beyond this point, additional debt can lead to a decline in both investments and growth.

It follows from the analysis theory of the debt Laffer Curve that, on the one hand, a reasonable evolution of the debt should be beneficial to investment and growth and, and on the other hand, the accumulation of heavy debt may hinder expansion. In sum, debt has a non-linear impact on investment and growth according to the defenders of this thesis. And it appears in these conditions that the debt would have an inverted U-shaped relationship with investment and growth.

1.2 Descriptive analysis of investment and debt financing SOEs

In this section, we will make a descriptive analysis of the evolution of the investments and the financing debts of the SOEs. To this end, it should be noted that during the period 1990-2016, the said indicators experienced a noticeable tangential rise from the 2000s.

Source: Author, data source Ministry of Finance of Morocco (DPEP)

Figure 1 : Evolution of SOEs' investment and their debt

SOEs investments increased from 16 billion Dirhams to 72,7 billion Dirhams during the period 1990-2016. This denotes an average annual growth rate of 6%. In addition, the trends in investments trends show three stages: the first phase (1990-2004) with an average investment of 18,5 billion Dirhams, the second phase (2005-2007) with an average investment of 40,9 Billion Dirhams and the third phase (2008-2016) where the average investment reaches 72,2 billion Dirhams.

Apart from the fact that the increase in investments is substantial, the variability is still limited and increases from 3,7 to 8,6 billion Dirhams, respectively, in the first two phases, and to a rating of 4,7 billion Dirhams third phase.

Regarding SOEs financing debts rose from 51,4 to 261,2 billion Dirhams during the period 1990-2016. This indicates an average annual growth rate of 6,5%. However, the trend of these debts accounts for the existence of two stages: the first phase (1990-2006) with a larger average debt of 65.4 billion Dirhams and the second phase between 2007 and 2015 with an average of 173,8 billion Dirhams. Similarly, it is during the last phase that annual fluctuations are very decisive with a rating of 53,3 billion Dirhams.

In relation to GDP, the investments and the financing debts of the SOEs respectively passed from 6,4% and 20,7% in 1990 to 7,2% and 25,7% in 2016 in increase respectively of 0,8 and

5 points for the period 1990-2016. In addition, their graph demonstrates a correlation Partially between them, hence our hypothesis:

“The public debt act positively on the investments of the SOEs”.

2. METHODOLOGY OF THE EMPIRICAL STUDY

Most theoretical and empirical studies have highlighted the impact of public debts on investments. In our study, we will try to see the effect of the public indebtedness, especially debt of the SOEs and external public debt on the investment of the SOEs.

2.1. Definition of study variables and data source

We will study the impact of the public debt on SOEs investments for Morocco for a 27-year period from 1990 to 2016. The variables of the study are presented in the following table:

Table 1 : Description of macroeconomic variables

Acronym	Variables Measurement	Definition	Data Source
Variable to explain			
SOEIN	SOEs investments (%GDP)	share of SOEs investments relative to GDP	Ministry of Finance of Morocco (DPEP)
Explanatory variables			
SOEFD	SOEs financing debts (%GDP)	share of SOEs financing debts in relation to GDP	Ministry of Finance of Morocco (DPEP)
CGDT	Central government debt, total (% of GDP)	Debt is the entire stock of direct government fixed-term contractual obligations to others outstanding on a particular date. It includes domestic and foreign liabilities such as currency and money deposits, securities other than shares, and loans. It is the gross amount of government liabilities reduced by the amount of equity and financial derivatives held by the government. Because debt is a stock rather than a flow, it is measured as of a given date, usually the last day of the fiscal year	Ministry of Finance of Morocco (DPEP), International Monetary Fund, Government Finance Statistics Yearbook and data files, and World Bank and OECD GDP estimates
EDS	External debt stocks (% of exports of goods, services and primary income)	Total external debt stocks to exports of goods, services and primary income	World Bank, International Debt Statistics
RIR	Real interest rate (%)	Real interest rate is the lending interest rate adjusted for inflation as measured by the GDP deflator. The terms and conditions attached to lending rates differ by country, however, limiting their comparability.	International Monetary Fund, International Financial Statistics and data files using World Bank data on the GDP

Acronym	Variables Measurement	Definition	Data Source
			deflator.
REERI	Real effective exchange rate index (2010 = 100)	Real effective exchange rate is the nominal effective exchange rate (a measure of the value of a currency against a weighted average of several foreign currencies) divided by a price deflator or index of costs.	International Monetary Fund, International Financial Statistics
IGDBD	Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)	Inflation as measured by the annual growth rate of the GDP implicit deflator shows the rate of price change in the economy as a whole. The GDP implicit deflator is the ratio of GDP in current local currency to GDP in constant local currency.	World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files

2.2. Method of analysis

To estimate our model, we will use the multiple regression by ordinary least squares (OLS).

The data processing of our chronological series is done using the software Eviews.

In this study, the selected SOEs investments function is as follows:

Equation (1): $SOEIN = f(SOEFD, CGDT, EDS, RIR, REERI, IGDBD)$

2.2.1. Correlations between variables

The degree of association between the variables is studied using the correlation. We only want to know the degree of inter-dependencies between the variables involved. When two phenomena have a common evolution we will say that they are correlated. (Greene, 2011)

The Pearson correlation coefficient is used to detect correlations between variables. The following table lists the correlations found using the Eviews software:

Table 2 : Correlation matrix

Variables	SOEIN	SOEFD	CGDT	EDS	RIR	REERI	IGDBD
SOEIN	1						
SOEFD	0.36656	1					
CGDT	-0.11909	0.59994	1				
EDS	-0.65823	0.22490	0.71015	1			
RIR	-0.57269	-0.65780	-0.55105	0.00790	1		
REERI	-0.68457	-0.42817	-0.35816	0.21352	0.86082	1	
IGDBD	-0.04822	0.10282	0.54852	0.43803	-0.51999	-0.30932	1

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

The correlation analysis between these seven variables shows, on the one hand, a positive correlation between SOEFD & CGDT (60%), CGDT & EDS (71%), RIR & REERI (86%) and CGDT & IGDBD (55%). On the other hand, a negative correlation between the following variables: SOEIN & EDS (-66%), SOEIN & RIR (-57%), SOEFD & RIR (-66%), CGDT & RIR (55%), SOEIN & REERI (-68%) and RIR & IGDBD (-52%).

2.2.2. Stationarity test

Before the processing of a time series, it is necessary to study the stochastic characteristics. If these characteristics ($E(x)$ and $Var(x)$) are modified in time, the time series is considered as non-stationary, otherwise the series is stationary. There are many tests for determining whether a series is stationary or nonstationary. The most popular one is the Augmented Dickey–Fuller test (ADF) (Dickey & Fuller, 1979). We will use the test for all of our variables.

The next table report the results of the ADF test at level using intercept, trend & intercept and none:

Table 3 : Unit root test for stationarity

Variables	Schwarz information Criterion		
	Intercept	Trend and intercept	None
SOEIN	-1.180512 (0.6671)	-1.302662 (0.8646)	0.275352 (0.7581)
SOEFD	-1.496618 (0.5181)	0.066211 (0.9950)	0.005340 (0.6745)
CGDT	-3.554891 (0.0143) **	-2.705123 (0.2426)	-1.179811 (0.2112)
EDS	-2.848747 (0.0694)	-1.450629 (0.8156)	-2.300321 (0.0239) **
RIR	-0.921207 (0.7635)	-6.899177 (0.0001) ***	-0.516803 (0.4820)
REERI	-1.480321 (0.5275)	-2.231885 (0.4536)	0.265943 (0.7554)
IGDBD	-4.253412 (0.0028) ***	-4.284499 (0.0117) ***	-3.376799 (0.0016) ***

*, ** and *** Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level.

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

Our variables, SOEIN, SOEFD, CGDT, EDS, RIR, REERI and IGDBD are found to be non-stationary at 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significance. Thus, the variables are non-stationary and not integrated of the same order.

Table (4) reports the results of the ADF test for first difference using constant, trend & constant, and none:

Table 4 : Result for unit roots test on the first difference

Variables	Schwarz info Criterion		
	Intercept	Trend and intercept	None
SOEIN	-4.206165 (0.0002) ***	-4.006642 (0.0220) **	-4.095368 (0.0042) ***
SOEFD	-2.010516 (0.2806)	-4.090813 (0.0204) **	-2.036520 (0.0421) **
CGDT	-9.615003 (0.0000) ***	-9.884146 (0.0000) ***	-9.925876 (0.0000) ***
EDS	-4.311214 (0.0025) ***	-4.434527 (0.0088) ***	-4.234196 (0.0002) ***
RIR	-6.549870 (0.0000) ***	-2.899886 (0.1839)	-3.357165 (0.0018) ***
REERI	-3.929389 (0.0062) ***	-4.097655 (0.0181) **	-4.005431 (0.0003) ***
IGDBD	-8.409421 (0.0000) ***	-8.520432 (0.0000) ***	-8.503141 (0.0000) ***

*, ** and *** Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level.

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

The all variables, SOEIN, SOEFD, CGDT, EDS, RIR, REERI and IGDBD are found to be integrated and stationary in both Intercept, Trend & intercept and None at 1% and 5% levels of significance. Thus, the variables are stationary and integrated of order one, i.e., $I(1)$.

2.2.3. Definition of co-integration

The objective of this study is to analyze the impact of public debt, especially external public debt and debt SOEs on investment SOEs. The model is written as follows:

Equation (2):

$$SOEIN_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 SOEFD_t + \beta_3 CGDT_t + \beta_4 EDS_t + \beta_5 RIR_t + \beta_6 REERI_t + \beta_7 IGDBD_t + \beta_8 time_t + u_t$$

we can rewrite this model as:

Equation (3):

$$u_t = SOEIN_t - (\beta_1 + \beta_2 SOEFD_t + \beta_3 CGDT_t + \beta_4 EDS_t + \beta_5 RIR_t + \beta_6 REERI_t + \beta_7 IGDBD_t + time_t)$$

With: t : 1990, ..., 2016.

After estimating the first equation we found that (u_t) to be stationary i.e., $I(0)$. The next table report the results of the ADF test for (u_t) at level using intercept, trend & intercept and none:

Table 5 : Unit root test for stationarity

Variables	Schwarz info Criterion		
	Intercept	Trend and intercept	None
u	-3.085282 (0.0402) **	-3.013811 (0.1475)	-3.168735 (0.0027) ***
*, ** and *** Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level.			

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

In that case, SOEIN, SOEFD, CGDT, EDS, RIR, REERI and IGDBD are co-integrated. The ‘equilibrating’ error term that corrects deviations of SOEIN from its equilibrium value given by the co-integration regression the relationship between the all variables can be expressed as an error correction mechanism (ECM):

Equation (4):

$$\Delta SOEIN_t = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta SOEFD_t + \alpha_3 \Delta CGDT_t + \alpha_4 \Delta EDS_t + \alpha_5 \Delta RIR_t + \alpha_6 \Delta REERI_t + \alpha_7 \Delta IGDBD_t + \alpha_8 u_{t-1} + \gamma_t$$

With: Δ the first difference operator; u_{t-1} the lagged value of the error correction term

γ_t a white noise error term; $t: 1990, \dots, 2016$.

Once the stationarity and co-integration tests are performed, error-correction models are estimated on the basis of which causality can be examined (Engle & Granger, 1987). The interest of these models is that they allow us, from the outset, to express the causality in the short and long run.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through this study, we will seek the relation between the investments of the SOEs and the public indebtedness, specially debt of the SOEs and externals public’s debts. we will use the multiple regression by OLS in the short-run and long-run.

The results of equation (2) for the long-run are as follows:

Table 6 : Results of Empirical Tests at long-run for the variable SOEIN

Variables	SOEFD	CGDT	EDS	RIR	REERI	IGDBD	TIME
Coefficient (Std. Error)	0.3143 (0.0845)	0.0034 (0.0405)	-0.0258 (0.0070)	0.0679 (0.1628)	-0.1531 (0.0897)	0.1163 (0.1560)	-0.1494 (0.0800)
t-Statistic (Prob.)	3.7213 (0.0014) ***	0.0832 (0.9345)	-3.6733 (0.0016) ***	0.4171 (0.6813)	-1.7060 (0.1043) *	0.7455 (0.4651)	-1.8664 (0.0775) *
R²	0.8752	F-statistic		19.0274	Prob (F-statistic)		0.0000 ***

*, ** and *** Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level.

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

And the results of equation (4) for the short-run are in the table (7):

Table 7 : Results of Empirical Tests at short-run for Δ PEEIN

Variables	Δ SOEFD	Δ CGDT	Δ EDS	Δ RIR	Δ REERI	Δ IGDBD	u_{t-1}
Coefficient (Std. Error)	0.2839 (0.0865)	-0.0254 (0.0254)	-0.0088 (0.0080)	0.0750 (0.0944)	-0.1073 (0.0632)	0.1038 (0.0892)	-0.6064 (0.2053)
t-Statistic (Prob.)	3.2826 (0.0041) ***	-0.9987 (0.3312)	-1.0934 (0.2886)	0.7946 (0.4372)	-1.6971 (0.1069)	1.1629 (0.2601)	-2.9545 (0.0085) ***
R²	0.5687	F-statistic		3.39038	Prob (F-statistic)		0.0173 **

*, ** and *** Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level.

Source: Author, estimates based on study data, Eviews

The following tables (6) & (7) show the following observations:

- Long-term R² and short-term R² are 0,875 and 0,569, respectively. This means that in the long-run our explanatory variables explain the SOEs investments of 88% and in the short-run the co-integration between the explanatory variables and SOEs investments is 57%.
- Subsequently, the long-term and short-run F-value of Fisher F gain is 0,000 and 0,017 respectively (significant respectively at 1% and 5%).
- All coefficients are individually statistically significant at the 61% or lower level;
- In a short-run, SOEs investments (SOEIN)/SOEs financing debts (SOEFD) elasticity 28%;

- The long-run value is given by the co-integrating regression, which is about 0,31 for SOEs financing debts (SOEFD), -0,03 for external debt stocks (EDS) and at -0,15 for real effective exchange rate index (REERI);
- In long and short run, SOEs investment is not affected by the real interest rate (RIR) and does not generate inflationary pressures;
- The coefficient of the error-correction term is -0,6. It means that, about 60% of the discrepancy between long-term and short-term, SOEs investments (SOEIN) is corrected within a year, i.e., a fast rate of adjustment to equilibrium.

CONCLUSION

Theoretical approaches were perplexed about the positive or negative link of debt to investment. In one hand, the results of our research have shown that, in the long-run, there is a positive relationship between SOEs investments and their debts. On the other hand, there is a negative relationship between SOEs investments with external debt stocks as well as with real effective exchange rate index. In short-run, the elasticity SOEs investments/SOEs financing debts is positive. In conclusion, the gap between long-term and short-term SOEs investments is corrected within a year. These conclusions confirmed our hypothesis.

Every research has its limits and ours is no exception to this rule. We used the Engle & Granger error-correction model, but beyond three variables, the model is weak because there could be more than one co-integration relationship once we go beyond two-time series. In order to remedy this identified weakness, it is better to use the Johansen method to test the co-integration relationships between several variables.

REFERENCE

- Barro, R. J. (1990). Government Spending in a Simple Model of Endogeneous Growth. Consulté à l'adresse <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/3451296>
- Claessens, S., & Diwan, I. (1990). Investment Incentives: New Money, Debt Relief, and the Critical Role of Conditionality in the Debt Crisis. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 4(1), 21-41. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wber/4.1.21>
- Cohen, D. (1993). Low Investment and Large LDC Debt in the 1980's. *American Economic Review*, 83(3), 437-449.
- Cohen, D. (1995). Large external debt and (slow) domestic growth a theoretical analysis. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 19(5), 1141-1163. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889\(94\)00822-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1889(94)00822-Y)

- Dickey, D. A., & Fuller, W. A. (1979). Distribution of the Estimators for Autoregressive Time Series With a Unit Root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 74(366), 427-431. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2286348>
- Dornbusch, R., & Reynoso, A. (1989). Financial Factors in Economic Development. *American Economic Review*, 79(2), 204-209. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w2889>
- Engle, R. F., & Granger, C. W. J. (1987). Co-Integration and Error Correction: Representation, Estimation, and Testing. *Econometrica*, 55(2), 251-276. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913236>
- Faruquee, R. R. (1992). *Private investment in sub-Saharan Africa: an exploratory analysis* (No. IDP120) (p. 1-0). The World Bank. Consulté à l'adresse <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/556071468914746694/Private-investment-in-sub-Saharan-Africa-an-exploratory-analysis>
- Greene, W. H. (2011). *Econometric Analysis* (7 edition). Boston: Pearson.
- Hayek, F. A. (1977). Toward a Free Market Monetary System. *The Gold and Monetary Conference*, 3(1), 8.
- Husain, A. (1997). Domestic taxes and external debt Laffer Curve. *Economica*, 64(255), 519-525.
- Meade, J. (1937). A Simplified Model of Mr. Keynes' System. *Review of Economic Studies*, 4(2), 98-107.
- Oshikoya, T. W. (1994). Macroeconomic Determinants of Domestic Private Investment in Africa: An Empirical Analysis. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 42(3), 573-596. <https://doi.org/10.1086/452103>
- Pattillo, C., Poirson, H., & Ricci, L. A. (2011). External Debt and Growth. *Review of Economics and Institutions*, 2(3). Consulté à l'adresse <https://ideas.repec.org/a/pia/review/v2y2011i3n2.html>
- R. Krugman, P. (1988). *Financing vs. Forgiving a Debt Overhang* (Vol. 29). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878\(88\)90044-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878(88)90044-2)
- Tabellini, G., & Alesina, A. (1989). External Debt, Capital Flight and Political Risk. Consulté à l'adresse <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/4553019>